

CAUSES OF STUDENTS' PRONUNCIATION ERRORS IN ENGLISH AND
STRATEGIES FOR ELIMINATING THEM

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Annotation. This article comprehensively studies pronunciation errors that affect communicative speech and their main causes, and shows methods for eliminating these problems. In addition, phonetic difficulties, the uniqueness of sounds in English, the influence of the native language, aspects related to stress and intonation are separately discussed and effective methods are recommended for improvement. As a result of the research conducted, the development of language skills is not only through regular exercises, but also through a conscious understanding of phonetic phenomena and a psychological approach.

Keywords: pronunciation, interference, vowels, prosodic errors, psychological and social factors, motivation, methods for improving pronunciation.

Introduction.

Learning English is not only about acquiring grammatical knowledge, but also about the ability to speak clearly and fluently in the process of communication. Pronunciation is one of the important components that form such effective communication. Speech that is not pronounced correctly leads to various misunderstandings, obstacles and reduces the effectiveness of communication. According to the results of the study, although many students have a sufficient vocabulary, they cannot express their thoughts clearly and fluently¹. Shu sababli, noto'g'ri talaffuz sabablarini aniqlash hamda ularga yechim topish hali ham dolzarb masalalardan biri bo'lib kelmoqda. Mazkur tadqiqotning maqsadi ingliz tilidagi talaffuz xatolarining asosiy sabablarini aniqlash hamda ularni bartaraf etishning samarali strategiyalarini o'rganishdan iborat.

Literature review.

One of the most frequently used areas in language learning skills is pronunciation errors that occur in communication. Since English is phonetically different from Uzbek, students often experience interference. This is a phenomenon in which phonetic rules and pronunciations in the native language are transferred to the new language and cause errors. Some sounds in English are absent in Uzbek, including the sound [ð] in the word this. As a result, students encounter problems in pronouncing these words. According to James Emil Flegel (1995), the absence of some sounds in English (for example, the sound [θ] in the English word think, the sound [ð] in the word this) forms incorrect pronunciation in students². He also studied the pronunciation of people of different nationalities in English and found that they replace new sounds with sounds in their native language. (For example, the English [θ] sound is pronounced as t or s). The presence of some complex vowels in English also creates difficulties for students. Because this language has a large number of vowels, some of which are pronounced short or long, and this serves to change the meaning. For example, in the English words full and fool, the vowel is pronounced short, and in the second one, the vowel is pronounced long. However, the same pronunciation of these words is observed in many students. Many students think that the sounds in a foreign language are the same as the sounds in their native language. Because of this, they pronounce the sounds [u:] and [ʊ] the same. In addition to sound, psychological fear and lack of motivation can also be a major factor in pronunciation errors. Many students do not speak in public because they are afraid of making mistakes. They think that they should speak perfectly and without mistakes from the very beginning, but they do not know that even excellent

¹ Kelly, G. *How to teach pronunciation*. London: Pearson Education, 2000. –P.12

² Flegel, J.E. *Second Language Speech Learning: Theory, Findings and Problems*. 1995. –P.233

specialists first learn by making mistakes. However, this situation is a major obstacle to the development of their pronunciation skills. Another reason is the lack of motivation among students. If students do not have an interest in English or any internal motivation, they will simply learn this language as a language, without paying attention to the rules of correct pronunciation³.

Methodology. The following scientific methods were used in this study. Working with minimal pairs. The most effective way to differentiate sounds is to work with minimal pairs. Through this, the student distinguishes each sound by comparing the different pronunciations in different words and does not confuse sounds with each other. The next method was the shadowing method. In this case, listening to a video or audio recording and imitating it, that is, repeating it exactly as it was spoken. At the next stage of the study, the method of writing transcription and studying it was used. Listening to the selected audio or video material and recording it allows for better understanding and differentiation of sounds along with pronunciation. The difficult words were selected from the recorded audio and compared with their transcription. In order to further clarify the results, the method of constant repetition of words was also used. Many students repeat words only during the learning process, but in their free time or while doing something, selecting words that are difficult for them and constantly repeating them is also a useful method. This method also helps to store words in permanent memory and prevent incorrect pronunciation. In the last part of the study, an analysis was conducted based on the mirror training approach, and various pronunciation exercises were performed using the mirror to see how to pronounce sounds, using lip, tongue, and jaw movements.

Conclusion

Incorrect pronunciation in English is a complex process that depends on many factors. To improve and completely eliminate these errors, students need to study phonetic knowledge in depth, practice regularly, and overcome obstacles caused by psychological as well as social factors. At the same time, they must always have a high level of self-confidence.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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³ Kelly, G. *How to Teach Pronunciation*. London: Longman, 2000. -P.45.

